

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. Motivation plays an important role in teaching foreign languages. Motivation is the reason for which humans and other animals initiate, continue, or terminate a behavior at a given time. Motivational states are commonly understood as forces acting within the agent that create a disposition to engage in goal-directed behavior. This article describes about the role of motivation in teaching foreign languages.

Motivation is the reason for which humans and other animals initiate, continue, or terminate a behavior at a given time. Motivational states are commonly understood as forces acting within the agent that create a disposition to engage in goal-directed behavior. It is often held that different mental states compete with each other and that only the strongest state determines behavior. This means that we can be motivated to do something without actually doing it. The paradigmatic mental state providing motivation is desire. But various other states, such as beliefs about what one ought to do or intentions, may also provide motivation. Motivation is derived from the word 'motive', which denotes a person's needs, desires, wants, or urges. It is the process of motivating individuals to take action in order to achieve a goal. The psychological elements fueling people's behavior in the context of job goals might include a desire for money.

As teachers get to know their students and find out their hobbies, interests, and passions, they can begin to build those into their lesson topics, activities, and assessments in class. For instance, if a teacher knows he or she has a handful of students motivated by sports or being active, a few who enjoy drawing, and some who are engaged by technology, that teacher could create a "menu" for an upcoming assessment. A menu of options for class activities allows the teacher to tap into

student engagement and motivation for many students at one time. Menu choices in this instance could include students showing what they have learned by creating a short video or class presentation, an opportunity to create a poster, infographic, or brochure that depicts what they have learned, or the chance to create an animated video or slideshow presenting the information learned. Creating a rubric for students ahead of time indicating the requirements that need to be included for whichever project is chosen is a great way to set the expectations necessary for the student's grade. Motivation and student engagement go hand-in-hand. A student who is engaged in what they are learning is motivated to learn, and a student who is motivated is going to be engaged in learning. Engaging and motivating learners can be challenging considering all classrooms are filled with students who have a wide variety of interests and abilities; it requires much effort and creativity from teachers.

Students who are motivated in their learning are going to show characteristics of being goal-oriented and are likely to see more success and higher achievement. Motivated learners take responsibility and initiative, show curiosity and a willingness to try, put forth genuine effort, and take pride in their work. Motivated learners are not going to give up after making a mistake, but instead, learn from those mistakes and be more likely to try again (this is called having a growth mindset). Going back to the aforementioned indices, these students are going to put forth effort and show persistence in their work, leading them to a higher level of achievement. For instance, motivation can:

- help us direct our attention toward tasks that need to be done,
- allow us to do these tasks in shorter periods of time as well as maintain attention during a longer time,
- minimize distractions and resist them better,
- affect how much information we retain and store,
- influence the perception of how easy or difficult tasks can appear.

Motivation is the state that can maintain students' attention and behavior as well as provides with more energy to needed to lead tasks to completion. Thus, it

can help sustain activities over a period of time. In education, motivation can have a variety of effects on students' behavior, preferences, and results. Most importantly, motivation urges to us perform an action. Without it, completing the action can be hard or even impossible.

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